

Probing deformed Kiselev-AdS Black Holes Surrounded by a Cloud of Strings through Thermodynamics, Radiative Features, and Shadow Observables

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We investigate the thermodynamic, radiative, and optical properties of a deformed Schwarzschild–Anti-de Sitter black hole surrounded by a cloud of strings and immersed in a quintessence field. The model is described by a static and spherically symmetric metric whose lapse function contains the string-cloud parameter γ , the quintessence parameters (\mathcal{N}, w) , the cosmological constant Λ , and the deformation parameters (α, β) . We derive the horizon thermodynamics in the extended phase space, including the Hawking temperature, thermodynamic volume, generalized first law, and Smarr relation. We also analyze the sparsity of Hawking radiation by using the geometric-optics absorption cross section determined by the critical impact parameter of null geodesics. The photon sphere and black-hole shadow are then studied numerically, showing how the deformation, string cloud, and quintessence contributions modify the characteristic optical radii. In the special limit $\beta \rightarrow 0$ with $\alpha = Q^2$, the metric reduces to a charged-like AdS geometry, so the deformation parameter plays the role of an effective charge squared. Finally, we compare the theoretical shadow radius with the Event Horizon Telescope constraints for M87* and Sgr A*, emphasizing that a complete constraint analysis requires a multidimensional scan of the parameter space.

I. INTRODUCTION

Black holes provide a unique arena in which gravitation, quantum theory, thermodynamics, and high-energy physics meet. Since the pioneering works of Bekenstein and Hawking, black holes have been understood as genuine thermodynamic systems characterized by entropy, temperature, and radiation [1–4]. In asymptotically Anti-de Sitter (AdS) spacetimes, the thermodynamic interpretation becomes even richer, because the cosmological constant can be treated as a thermodynamic pressure and the black-hole mass as enthalpy in the extended phase-space framework [5–8]. This point of view has revealed phase transitions, stability properties, and critical phenomena that are relevant not only for classical gravity but also for gauge/gravity duality and related approaches to quantum gravity.

Another important direction in black-hole physics concerns the influence of external matter fields and nontrivial surrounding media on the spacetime geometry. Among such sources, a cloud of strings is particularly interesting. Letelier [9] first introduced the concept of a cloud of strings in 1979, which may be regarded as a one-dimensional analogue of a cloud of dust. A black hole surrounded by a string cloud can be interpreted as a purely energetic field configuration, where the radial distribution of strings is balanced by an effective negative pressure that counteracts the inward gravitational pull [10]. One notable example in four dimensions is the global monopole configuration. The presence of a string cloud acts as an additional source of gravity, modifying the Schwarzschild solution and consequently altering the spacetime geometry [11]. In

particular, it leads to an increase in the radius of the event horizon compared to the standard Schwarzschild case. An important outcome of studying Einstein’s field equations in the presence of a string cloud is that relativistic string distributions can provide useful phenomenological models for gravitational interactions. Studies of black-hole solutions in the presence of a cloud of strings within the framework of Einstein gravity, as well as in various modified gravity theories, have been extensively investigated in the literature [12–21].

Cosmological observations indicate that the present Universe is undergoing accelerated expansion, usually attributed to a dark-energy component with negative pressure. Quintessence represents one of the simplest dynamical models of dark energy, described by an equation-of-state parameter w in the range $-1 < w < -1/3$ [22, 23]. In black-hole physics, the Kiselev-type construction provides an effective way to incorporate a surrounding quintessence field into a static and spherically symmetric geometry [24]. The presence of quintessence modifies the asymptotic structure, the horizon equation, the thermodynamic quantities, and the propagation of null geodesics. Therefore, black holes immersed in a quintessence field are useful theoretical laboratories for investigating possible connections between strong gravitational fields and large-scale cosmological backgrounds.

In recent years, black-hole shadows and photon-sphere observables have become especially important due to the horizon-scale images of M87* and Sgr A* reported by the Event Horizon Telescope Collaboration [25–30]. The shadow boundary is governed by unstable circular null orbits and therefore encodes information about the near-horizon geometry. Since matter distributions, effective charges, deformation parameters, and cosmological fields can shift the photon-sphere radius and the critical impact parameter, shadow observables offer a complementary way to test deviations from the standard Schwarzschild or Schwarzschild–AdS scenarios. At the same time, the same optical structure controls the

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high-frequency absorption cross section, which is directly related to the energy emission rate and the sparsity of Hawking radiation.

Geometric deformations of black-hole metrics constitute another useful route for parametrizing deviations from the standard Schwarzschild–AdS geometry. Such deformations may arise as effective descriptions of modified gravitational dynamics, nonlinear matter sectors, or regularization mechanisms that smooth the short-distance behavior of the gravitational field. In the model considered here, the deformation is controlled by the pair (α, β) : the parameter α sets the strength of the deformation, while β introduces a characteristic length scale. This structure is flexible enough to interpolate between genuinely deformed geometries and a charged-like limit, making it possible to separate the effects produced by the surrounding matter fields from those associated with the intrinsic deformation of the black-hole background [31, 32].

Motivated by these developments, in the present study we investigate a static, spherically symmetric deformed Schwarzschild–AdS black hole surrounded by a cloud of strings (CS) and immersed in a quintessence field (QF). The terminology used throughout the paper is fixed by the matter content of the metric: the parameters (\mathcal{N}, w) describe the Kiselev-type quintessence sector, while γ characterizes the cloud of strings. The parameters (α, β) encode the geometric deformation, with the special limit $\beta \rightarrow 0$ and $\alpha = Q^2$ reducing the metric to a charged-like AdS form. This limiting case is useful for interpretation, although away from it the deformation should not be identified with an ordinary electromagnetic charge.

The main purpose of this work is to analyze how the combined effects of deformation, string cloud, and quintessence modify the thermodynamic, radiative, and optical properties of the black hole. We first study the horizon thermodynamics in the extended phase space, deriving the Hawking temperature, thermodynamic volume, generalized first law, conjugate quantities, and Smarr relation. We then examine the sparsity of Hawking radiation by combining the Hawking temperature with the geometric-optics capture cross section determined by the photon sphere. Subsequently, we analyze null geodesics, the effective potential, photon trajectories, the photon-sphere radius, and the black-hole shadow. Finally, we compare the theoretical shadow radius with the EHT-inferred intervals for M87* and Sgr A*, emphasizing that the numerical comparison presented here should be regarded as a representative consistency check rather than a complete multidimensional observational constraint.

II. SPHERICALLY SYMMETRIC ADS DEFORMED-BH WITH CS IMMERSSED IN QF

In this section, we consider a static, spherically symmetric deformed Schwarzschild–AdS black hole [31], surrounded by a cloud of strings and immersed in a Kiselev-type quintessence background. Various aspects of related spacetimes have been studied in the literature, including thermodynamics [32], geodesic motion and scalar perturbations with a global monopole surrounded by QF [33], holographic Einstein rings [34], accretion disks [35], geodesic structure and thermodynamics with CS [36], and extensions involving additional matter distributions [37].

Building upon these studies, we examine how the geometric deformation, QF, and CS modify the spacetime curvature and consequently influence key observables, such as the photon sphere, black-hole shadow, and photon trajectories. In addition, we analyze the thermodynamic properties of the system, exploring how the combined effects of deformation, QF, and CS alter the horizon temperature, thermodynamic potentials, and radiative sparsity of the black hole.

To obtain the deformed AdS-Schwarzschild black hole solution with CS and immersed in QF, we start with the four-dimensional action as [31]

$$S = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \left(\frac{R - 2\Lambda}{2\kappa} + L_m + L_X \right), \quad (1)$$

where g is the determinant of the metric, R is the Ricci scalar, Λ is the cosmological constant, L_m is the usual matter Lagrangian, and L_X represents Lagrangian for additional matter fields.

The variation of the action with respect to the metric gives the field equations

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \kappa T_{\mu\nu}^{(m)} + T_{\mu\nu}^X. \quad (2)$$

To include string-like objects, we consider the Nambu–Goto action given by [9]

$$\begin{aligned} S_{CS} &= \int \sqrt{-h} \mathcal{M} d\lambda^0 d\lambda^1 \\ &= \int \mathcal{M} \sqrt{-\frac{1}{2} \Sigma^{\mu\nu} \Sigma_{\mu\nu}} d\lambda^0 d\lambda^1, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{M} is the dimensionless constant that characterizes the string, (λ^0, λ^1) are the timelike and spacelike coordinate parameters, respectively [38]. h is the determinant of the induced metric of the strings world sheet given by $h_{ab} = g_{\mu\nu} \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \lambda^a} \frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial \lambda^b}$. $\Sigma^{\mu\nu} = \epsilon^{ab} \frac{\partial x^\mu}{\partial \lambda^a} \frac{\partial x^\nu}{\partial \lambda^b}$ is the bivector related to the string world sheet, where ϵ^{ab} is the second rank Levi-Civita tensor which takes the non-zero values as $\epsilon^{01} = -\epsilon^{10} = 1$.

The energy-momentum tensor of string-like objects is given by

$$T_{\mu\nu}^{CS} = 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial g_{\mu\nu}} \mathcal{M} \sqrt{-\frac{1}{2} \Sigma^{\mu\nu} \Sigma_{\mu\nu}} = \frac{\rho^{CS} \Sigma_{\alpha\nu} \Sigma_\mu^\alpha}{\sqrt{-h}}, \quad (4)$$

where ρ^{CS} is the proper density of the string cloud. The energy-momentum tensor components are given by

$$T_t^{t(CS)} = -\frac{\gamma}{r^2} = T_r^{r(CS)}, \quad T_\theta^{\theta(CS)} = T_\phi^{\phi(CS)} = 0, \quad (5)$$

Here, γ is a dimensionless constant associated with string-like objects.

The energy-momentum tensor for quintessence field is given by [24]

$$\begin{aligned} T^t_t|_{QF} &= T^r_r|_{QF} = \rho_q = -\frac{3\mathcal{N}w}{r^{3(w+1)}}, \\ T^\theta_\theta|_{QF} &= T^\phi_\phi|_{QF} = -\frac{\rho_q(3w+1)}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The energy density itself is fixed by demanding $\nabla_\mu T^\mu_\nu = 0$, which reduces to $d\rho_q/dr + 3(w+1)\rho_q/r = 0$. The matching scalar profile follows from $X = \rho_q(1+w)/2$ and $V = \rho_q(1-w)/2$, giving $\varphi(r) \propto r^{(1-3w)/2}$ in the weak-field limit and an inverse power-law potential $V(\varphi) \propto |\varphi|^{-6(w+1)/(1-3w)}$ that is well known for tracker quintessence [39–41].

Thus, incorporating both the cloud of strings and the quintessence field, the metric corresponding to the deformed AdS black hole [31] is described by the following line element

$$ds^2 = -f(r) dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{f(r)} + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\varphi^2), \quad (7)$$

where the lapse function is given by

$$f(r) = 1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r} + \alpha \left[\frac{\beta^2}{3r(\beta+r)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta+r)^2} \right] - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r^{3w+1}}, \quad (8)$$

Here, M represents the mass of the black hole, γ is the string-cloud parameter, (\mathcal{N}, w) are the QF parameters, Λ is the cosmological constant, and α and β are positive free parameters, with β having dimensions of length. The sign of the parameter γ must satisfy $\gamma > 0$ to ensure positive string tension density and a consistent geometric deficit. Values $\gamma > 1$ may lead to pathological asymptotics.

- When $\alpha = 0$, the metric function reduces to

$$f(r) = 1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r} - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r^{3w+1}}. \quad (9)$$

In this case, the spacetime reduces to the Schwarzschild–AdS black hole surrounded by CS immersed in QF [42].

- When $\beta = 0$ (with $\alpha = Q^2$), the metric function becomes

$$f(r) = 1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r} + \frac{\alpha}{r^2} - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r^{3w+1}}. \quad (10)$$

In this limit, the spacetime corresponds to a charged-like AdS black hole with CS immersed in QF [43].

Figure 1 summarizes how the metric function responds to the main model parameters. Panel (a) shows that the deformation strength α mostly affects the small- and intermediate-radius region, where the regularizing deformation terms are most important. Panel (b) shows that changing β/M modifies the length scale over which the deformation contributes to the lapse function. Panel (c) displays the effect of the string cloud: increasing γ lowers the constant part of $f(r)$ and shifts the horizon structure. Panel (d) shows that the QF normalization $\mathcal{N}M$ changes the large-radius behavior for $w = -2/3$, because the QF term is linear in r in this case. These trends determine the horizon location and therefore feed directly into the thermodynamic and optical observables analyzed below.

III. THERMODYNAMIC PROPERTIES

We begin this section by exploring the thermodynamics of the deformed AdS black hole surrounded by a CS and immersed in a QF. To achieve this, we first analyze the geometric temperature of the system. The Hawking temperature T is obtained from the surface gravity $\kappa = f'(r_h)/2$ through $T = \kappa/(2\pi)$ [1–3], namely

$$T = \frac{f'(r_h)}{4\pi} = \frac{1}{4\pi r_h} \left[1 - \gamma + \frac{\alpha}{(\beta+r_h)^2} - \frac{\alpha\beta^2}{(\beta+r_h)^4} - \frac{2\alpha r_h}{(\beta+r_h)^3} - \Lambda r_h^2 + \frac{3w\mathcal{N}}{r_h^{3w+1}} \right], \quad (11)$$

where the BH mass parameter M at horizon will be

$$M = \frac{r_h}{2} \left[1 - \gamma + \alpha \left(\frac{\beta^2}{3r_h(\beta+r_h)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta+r_h)^2} \right) - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r_h^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r_h^{3w+1}} \right] \quad (12)$$

For $w = -2/3$, the QF contribution to Eq. (11) becomes $3w\mathcal{N}/r_h^{3w+1} = -2\mathcal{N}r_h$, whereas the AdS contribution $-\Lambda r_h^2$ is positive for $\Lambda < 0$. Therefore, at small and intermediate horizon radii the deformation and matter sectors compete with the Schwarzschild-like contribution, while at large r_h the AdS term drives the temperature upward. This produces the familiar Schwarzschild–AdS minimum of the Hawking temperature, shifted by the parameters $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \mathcal{N})$.

In Fig. 2, we plot the Hawking temperature T_H as a function of the horizon radius r_h . The numerical curves are obtained by fixing the reference mass scale to $M = 1$, which allows the axes to be written directly in the usual form T_H versus r_h .

Figure 2 illustrates the parameter dependence of the Hawking temperature. Panel (a) shows that the deformation strength α mainly affects the small-horizon branch, where the deformation terms in Eq. (11) are most relevant. Panel (b) indicates that increasing β changes the regularizing scale of the deformation and shifts the low-radius portion of the temperature curve. Panel (c) shows that the string cloud reduces the overall temperature because it enters Eq. (11) through the factor $1 - \gamma$. Panel (d) shows that the QF normalization \mathcal{N} also suppresses the temperature for $w = -2/3$, consistently with the negative contribution $-2\mathcal{N}r_h$.

The entropy of the system is obtained from the first law of thermodynamics $dM = TdS$ (while keeping others fixed)

$$S = \int \frac{dM}{T} = \pi r_h^2 \quad (13)$$

which is a quarter of the Bekestein–Hawking horizon area.

In extended phase space, the cosmological constant is considered as thermodynamic pressure related by [44–46]

$$P = -\frac{\Lambda}{8\pi}. \quad (14)$$

Thereby, the BH mass M in terms of P can be expressed as,

$$M = \frac{r_h}{2} \left[1 - \gamma + \alpha \left(\frac{\beta^2}{3r_h(\beta+r_h)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta+r_h)^2} \right) + \frac{8\pi P}{3} r_h^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r_h^{3w+1}} \right] \quad (15)$$

Hence, the thermodynamic volume is

$$V = \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial P} \right)_{r_h, \mathcal{N}} = \frac{4\pi}{3} r_h^3. \quad (16)$$

Treating $M = M(r_h, P, \alpha, \beta, \mathcal{N}, \gamma)$, the modified first law of thermodynamics [47]

$$dM = TdS + VdP + \Psi_\gamma d\gamma + \Psi_\alpha d\alpha + \Psi_\beta d\beta + \Psi_{\mathcal{N}} d\mathcal{N}, \quad (17)$$

where T is the thermodynamic temperature which is equal to the Hawking temperature, V is the thermodynamic volume,

FIG. 1. Metric function $f(r)$ for the deformed Schwarzschild–AdS black hole surrounded by a cloud of strings and immersed in a QF. The reference configuration is $M = 1$, $\alpha = 1$, $\beta/M = 0.1$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $\mathcal{N}M = 0.01$, $w = -2/3$, and $\Lambda M^2 = -0.03$, while one parameter is varied at a time. Panel (a) varies the deformation strength α , panel (b) varies the deformation length scale β/M , panel (c) varies the string-cloud parameter γ , and panel (d) varies the QF normalization $\mathcal{N}M$. The zeros of $f(r)$ determine the horizon positions, whereas the shape of the curves controls the near-horizon redshift and the subsequent thermodynamic and optical properties.

FIG. 2. Hawking temperature T_H as a function of the horizon radius r_h for the deformed Schwarzschild–AdS black hole surrounded by a cloud of strings and immersed in a QF. The reference mass scale is fixed as $M = 1$ in the numerical evaluation. The four panels show the variation of a single parameter while the remaining ones are fixed at the reference values $\alpha = 1$, $\beta = 0.1$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $\mathcal{N} = 0.01$, $w = -2/3$, and $\Lambda = -0.03$: (a) variation of α , (b) variation of β , (c) variation of γ , and (d) variation of \mathcal{N} . Only the positive-temperature branch is displayed. The curves exhibit a minimum temperature, characteristic of AdS black-hole thermodynamics. Increasing γ or \mathcal{N} lowers the temperature branch in the explored interval, while the deformation parameters modify both the small-radius behavior and the location of the minimum.

and the remaining conjugate quantities are as follows:

$$\Psi_\gamma = \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial \gamma} \right) = -\frac{r_h}{2}, \quad (18)$$

$$\Psi_\alpha = \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial \alpha} \right) = \frac{\beta^2}{6(\beta + r_h)^3} + \frac{r_h}{2(\beta + r_h)^2}, \quad (19)$$

$$\Psi_\beta = \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial \beta} \right) = -\frac{\alpha(\beta^2 + 4\beta r_h + 6r_h^2)}{6(\beta + r_h)^4}, \quad (20)$$

$$\Psi_{\mathcal{N}} = \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial \mathcal{N}} \right) = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{r_h^{3w}}. \quad (21)$$

With these expressions, one can verify, using Euler's theorem, that the Smarr relation [48]

$$M = 2(TS - PV) + 2\alpha\Psi_\alpha + \beta\Psi_\beta + (3w + 1)\mathcal{N}\Psi_{\mathcal{N}} \quad (22)$$

holds for the present case. Since γ is dimensionless, it does not contribute to the Euler scaling and therefore does not appear explicitly in the Smarr relation. Moreover, in the limit $\beta \rightarrow 0$ with $\alpha = Q^2$, the deformation term becomes Q^2/r^2 , and the metric reduces to a charged-like AdS solution surrounded by

CS and QF. This observation clarifies why α behaves as an effective charge squared only in this limiting regime.

In the canonical ensemble of enthalpy M , the Gibbs free energy is defined by

$$G = M - TS = \frac{r_h}{4} \left[1 - \gamma + \frac{\alpha}{(\beta + r_h)^2} + \frac{2\alpha\beta^2}{3r_h(\beta + r_h)^3} + \frac{\alpha\beta^2}{(\beta + r_h)^4} + \frac{2\alpha r_h}{(\beta + r_h)^3} - \frac{16\pi P}{3} r_h^2 - \frac{(2 + 3w)\mathcal{N}}{r_h^{3w+1}} \right]. \quad (23)$$

For the state parameter $w = -2/3$, the QF contribution $-\frac{(2+3w)\mathcal{N}}{r_h^{3w+1}}$ vanishes.

Figure 3 shows the Gibbs free energy G as a function of the Hawking temperature, displayed as $20T$, for three representative values of the string-cloud parameter γ . The blue, purple, and red curves correspond to $\gamma = 0.05$, $\gamma = 0.10$, and $\gamma = 0.15$, respectively. The curves exhibit a characteristic nonmonotonic behavior: G rises along the low-temperature branch, reaches a maximum, and then decreases at higher temperatures. Increasing γ lowers the Gibbs free energy in

FIG. 3. Gibbs free energy G as a function of the Hawking temperature, plotted as $20T$, for three values of the string-cloud parameter γ . The remaining parameters are fixed as $\mathcal{N} = 0.01$, $w = -2/3$, $P = 0.03/(8\pi)$, $\alpha = 1$, and $\beta = 0.5$. The blue, purple, and red curves correspond to $\gamma = 0.05$, $\gamma = 0.10$, and $\gamma = 0.15$, respectively. The absence of a swallow-tail structure indicates that no first-order phase transition appears in the displayed parameter range, although the local maximum signals a change in the thermodynamic behavior between small- and large-radius branches.

the intermediate-temperature region, while the curves tend to approach each other at larger temperatures. The absence of a swallow-tail structure indicates that no first-order phase transition occurs within the chosen parameter range; nevertheless, the local maximum signals a change in the thermodynamic behavior between the small- and large-radius branches.

IV. SPARSITY OF HAWKING RADIATION

Hawking emission from an asymptotically flat Schwarzschild black hole is known to be sparse: the typical time interval between the emission of successive quanta is much larger than the characteristic oscillation period of an emitted quantum [49, 50]. In the present geometry, the same diagnostic can be formulated locally by combining the Hawking temperature with the effective capture cross section of the photon sphere. This provides a useful way to quantify how the deformation, the string cloud, and the quintessence background affect the intermittency of the emitted flux. Similar sparsity diagnostics have also been employed recently in radiative analyses of regular black holes, including works by the present authors [51, 52].

Throughout this section, all quantities are expressed in Planck units, so that $G = c = \hbar = k_B = 1$. In the geometric-optics approximation, which relates the high-frequency absorption cross section to the photon-sphere capture area [53–55], the number flux of massless bosonic quanta can be written as

$$\Gamma = \frac{g \zeta(3)}{4\pi^2} \sigma_{\text{lim}} T^3, \quad (24)$$

where g is the number of radiating degrees of freedom, $\zeta(3)$ is Apéry's constant, T is the Hawking temperature given in Eq. (11), and σ_{lim} is the high-frequency absorption cross section. For a static and spherically symmetric black hole, this cross section is determined by the critical impact parameter

b_c of null geodesics,

$$\sigma_{\text{lim}} = \pi b_c^2, \quad b_c^2 = \frac{r_s^2}{f(r_s)}, \quad (25)$$

where r_s is the photon-sphere radius obtained from Eq. (45). Therefore,

$$\sigma_{\text{lim}} = \pi \frac{r_s^2}{f(r_s)}. \quad (26)$$

The mean time gap between successive emissions is $\tau_{\text{gap}} = 1/\Gamma$. To define the localization time of an emitted quantum, we take the peak of the number spectrum, $\omega_{\text{peak}} = x_n T$, where $x_n \simeq 1.59362$ solves $e^x(2-x) = 2$ [50]. Thus,

$$\tau_{\text{oc}} = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_{\text{peak}}} = \frac{2\pi}{x_n T}. \quad (27)$$

The sparsity parameter is then

$$\eta = \frac{\tau_{\text{gap}}}{\tau_{\text{oc}}} = \frac{\omega_{\text{peak}}}{2\pi\Gamma} = \frac{2\pi x_n}{g \zeta(3) \sigma_{\text{lim}} T^2} = \frac{2x_n}{g \zeta(3)} \frac{f(r_s)}{r_s^2 T^2}. \quad (28)$$

A value $\eta \gg 1$ corresponds to sparse radiation, whereas $\eta \lesssim 1$ indicates a nearly continuous flux. Since T , r_s , and $f(r_s)$ all depend on $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \mathcal{N}, w, \Lambda)$, Eq. (28) gives a compact diagnostic of the influence of the external matter and deformation parameters on the Hawking cascade.

For the present solution, an increase in the string-cloud parameter γ lowers the asymptotic constant part of the lapse function and generally shifts the photon sphere outward. The quintessence contribution also modifies both T and r_s , with the sign and magnitude of the effect controlled by (\mathcal{N}, w) . The deformation parameters (α, β) enter the sparsity in two competing ways: they change the horizon temperature through Eq. (11) and change the optical capture area through Eq. (26). Consequently, the radiation cannot be characterized by the temperature alone; the optical sector must also be included. This is precisely the role of Eq. (28).

In the small-angle and geometric-optics regime used below for the shadow analysis, the same critical impact parameter controls both the high-frequency absorption cross section and the apparent shadow size. The sparsity of Hawking radiation and the shadow radius are therefore linked through the photon-sphere structure, although they probe different physical aspects of the spacetime: R_{sh} is an optical observable for external photons, while η measures the temporal separation of emitted Hawking quanta.

Figure 4 confirms that the Hawking cascade is not continuous in the parameter ranges considered here. The quantity η remains larger than unity, and in several regions it is more than one order of magnitude above unity. The deformation parameter α enhances the maximum of $\log_{10} \eta$ in panel (a), whereas increasing β/M modifies the small-radius behavior and changes the depth of the first minimum in panel (b). The string-cloud parameter γ in panel (c) and the QF normalization \mathcal{N} in panel (d) mainly shift the intermediate-radius peak because both parameters alter the photon-sphere radius and the temperature simultaneously. These plots demonstrate that the sparsity must be discussed together with the optical sector, rather than from T alone.

V. ENERGY EMISSION RATE

The energy emission rate of a black hole in the high-frequency regime is heavily influenced by its geometric con-

FIG. 4. Sparsity parameter $\log_{10} \eta$ as a function of r_h/M . The panels follow the same reference configuration used in Fig. 2: $\alpha = 1$, $\beta/M = 0.1$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $\mathcal{N}M = 0.01$, $w = -2/3$, and $\Lambda M^2 = -0.03$, while one parameter is varied at a time. Panel (a) varies α , panel (b) varies β/M , panel (c) varies γ , and panel (d) varies $\mathcal{N}M$. Since all displayed curves satisfy $\log_{10} \eta > 0$, the radiation is sparse throughout the explored domain. The nonmonotonic profile reflects the competition between the Hawking temperature and the photon-sphere capture area entering Eq. (28).

figuration and horizon properties. Quantum mechanically, a black hole can evaporate by emitting Hawking radiation [3, 49]. Radiative observables based on the Hawking temperature, sparsity, and spectral energy emission have also been analyzed in recent works by the present authors [51, 52]. The differential rate of energy emission per unit frequency ω and unit time t is given by

$$\frac{d^2 \mathbb{E}}{d\omega dt} = \frac{2\pi^2 \sigma_{\text{lim}}}{e^{\omega/T_H} - 1} \omega^3, \quad (29)$$

where ω is the emitted frequency, T_H is the Hawking temperature, and σ_{lim} is the high-frequency limiting absorption cross section. This expression shows that the emission spectrum is controlled by two different sectors of the geometry: the thermal sector, through T_H , and the optical sector, through σ_{lim} .

Furthermore, in the high-frequency limit, the absorption cross section oscillates around a constant limiting value σ_{lim} , which geometrically corresponds to the capture area associated with the black-hole shadow [53–55]. Using (see Section VI for the shadow radius R_{sh} formula)

$$\sigma_{\text{lim}} = \pi R_{\text{sh}}^2 = \pi r_s^2 \frac{f(r_0)}{f(r_s)}, \quad (30)$$

and substituting the Hawking temperature in Eq. (11) into Eq. (29), we obtain

$$\frac{d^2 \mathbb{E}}{d\omega dt} = \frac{2\pi^3 r_s^2 f(r_0) \omega^3}{f(r_s) [\exp(\frac{4\pi r_h \omega}{\Delta}) - 1]}, \quad (31)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} f(r_s) &= 1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r_s} + \alpha \left[\frac{\beta^2}{3r_s(\beta + r_s)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta + r_s)^2} \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r_s^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r_s^{3w+1}}, \\ f(r_0) &= 1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r_0} + \alpha \left[\frac{\beta^2}{3r_s(\beta + r_0)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta + r_0)^2} \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r_0^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r_0^{3w+1}}, \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta &= 1 - \gamma + \frac{\alpha}{(\beta + r_h)^2} - \frac{\alpha\beta^2}{(\beta + r_h)^4} - \frac{2\alpha r_h}{(\beta + r_h)^3} \\ &\quad - \Lambda r_h^2 + \frac{3w\mathcal{N}}{r_h^{3w+1}}. \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

Since $T_H = \Delta/(4\pi r_h)$, Eq. (31) makes explicit how the peak and magnitude of the emission spectrum are affected by the same parameters that determine the horizon temperature and the photon-sphere capture area.

Figure 5 displays the spectral energy emission rate for the same class of parameter variations considered in the thermodynamic and sparsity analyses. All panels exhibit the expected Planck-like profile. At very small ω , the factor ω^3 suppresses the emission rate. At intermediate frequencies, the competition between the polynomial factor ω^3 and the Bose-Einstein denominator produces a maximum. At large ω , the exponential factor $\exp(\omega/T_H)$ dominates, causing the spectrum to rapidly decay. Therefore, the position and height of the peak encode the combined influence of the Hawking temperature and of the geometric-optics absorption cross section.

Panel (a) shows that increasing the deformation strength α reduces the height of the emission peak for the chosen reference configuration. This behavior follows from the simultaneous modification of T_H and σ_{lim} : the deformation changes the near-horizon temperature through Eq. (11) and also changes the photon-sphere radius entering Eq. (30). Panel (b) indicates that increasing the deformation scale β shifts the emission profile upward and slightly modifies the peak location. In this case, the regularizing length scale of the deformation affects both the thermal factor and the optical capture area, enhancing the emitted power in the displayed frequency range.

Panels (c) and (d) show the effects of the surrounding matter fields. Increasing the string-cloud parameter γ lowers the emission rate and shifts the peak downward. This is consistent with the fact that γ reduces the constant part of the lapse function and lowers the Hawking temperature branch in the parameter range explored in Fig. 2. Similarly, increasing the QF normalization \mathcal{N} suppresses the spectrum for $w = -2/3$, because the corresponding contribution to the temperature is negative, $3w\mathcal{N}/r_h^{3w+1} = -2\mathcal{N}r_h$. Thus, both the cloud of strings and the quintessence background tend to weaken the

FIG. 5. Energy emission rate $d^2\mathbb{E}/(d\omega dt)$ as a function of the emitted frequency ω for the deformed Schwarzschild–AdS black hole surrounded by a cloud of strings and immersed in a QF. The reference configuration is fixed as $M = 1$, $r_h = 2.0$, $\alpha = 1$, $\beta = 0.1$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $\mathcal{N} = 0.01$, $w = -2/3$, and $\Lambda = -0.03$, while one parameter is varied at a time. Panel (a) varies α , panel (b) varies β , panel (c) varies γ , and panel (d) varies \mathcal{N} . The curves show the characteristic Hawking spectrum: the emission rate starts from zero at small frequency, reaches a maximum at an intermediate frequency, and then decays exponentially at high frequency.

Hawking energy output for the representative configuration used here.

The behavior in Fig. 5 complements the sparsity analysis. While Fig. 4 quantifies the temporal separation between successive emitted quanta, Fig. 5 shows how the emitted energy is distributed over frequency. Since both observables depend on σ_{lim} and T_H , the optical structure governed by the photon sphere is not merely relevant for the shadow: it also controls the effective radiating area of the black hole in the high-frequency approximation.

VI. BLACK HOLE SHADOW AND PARAMETERS CONSTRAINT

Null geodesic motion is central to black hole physics because it governs how photons propagate through the curved spacetime surrounding a black hole. The properties of these null geodesics reveal key features such as the photon sphere, the black hole shadow, and the possible trajectories of light near the event horizon. As a result, they form the theoretical foundation for interpreting a wide range of astrophysical and observational phenomena associated with black holes [56, 57]. The first horizon-scale images of the supermassive black holes *M87** [25–27] and *Sgr A** [28–30], obtained by the Event Horizon Telescope (EHT), have stimulated significant interest in black-hole models in general relativity as well as in modified gravity theories.

The spacetime Eq. (7) can be expressed as $ds^2 = g_{\mu\nu}dx^\mu dx^\nu$, where the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ with $\mu, \nu = 0, \dots, 3$ is given by

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \text{diag} \left(-f(r), \frac{1}{f(r)}, r^2, r^2 \sin^2 \theta \right), \quad (34)$$

In this section, we investigate null geodesic motion using the Lagrangian formalism, which provides a powerful and systematic framework for analyzing photon trajectories in curved spacetime. Within this approach, the Lagrangian associated with a test particle moving in a gravitational background described by the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ is given by [56, 57]

$$\mathbb{L} = \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} \dot{x}^\mu \dot{x}^\nu, \quad (35)$$

where a dot denotes differentiation with respect to λ , an affine parameter along the geodesic.

Considering the geodesic motion on the equatorial plane defined by $\theta = \pi/2$, the Lagrangian density function Eq. (35) using Eq. (34) explicitly can be written as

$$\mathbb{L} = \frac{1}{2} \left[-f(r)\dot{t}^2 + \frac{1}{f(r)}\dot{r}^2 + r^2\dot{\phi}^2 \right]. \quad (36)$$

One can see that the Lagrangian density function is independent of the temporal coordinate t and the azimuthal angular coordinate ϕ . Therefore, there exist two conserved quantities associated with these cyclic coordinates. These are called the energy of particles given by

$$E = f(r)\dot{t}, \quad (37)$$

and the conserved angular momentum by

$$L = r^2\dot{\phi}. \quad (38)$$

Based on the above, the radial equation of motion for photon particles can be expressed as

$$\dot{r}^2 + V_{\text{eff}} = E^2, \quad (39)$$

which is equivalent to one-dimensional equation of motion of particles. Here V_{eff} is the effective potential of the system that governs the photon dynamics and is given by

$$V_{\text{eff}} = \frac{L^2}{r^2} f(r) = \frac{L^2}{r^2} \left[1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r} + \alpha \left\{ \frac{\beta^2}{3r(\beta+r)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta+r)^2} \right\} - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r^{3w+1}} \right]. \quad (40)$$

From the above expression, it is evident that the effective potential governing the photon dynamics is strongly influenced by the geometric and physical parameters of the spacetime. These parameters include the black hole mass M , the string cloud parameter γ , the quintessence normalization parameter \mathcal{N} , the deformation parameters (α, β) , as well as the cosmological constant Λ . Consequently, the behavior of null geodesics and the structure of photon orbits are highly sensitive to variations in these quantities.

FIG. 6. Effective potential $V_{\text{eff}}(r)$ for null geodesics in the equatorial plane. The parameters are fixed as $M = 1$, $\alpha = 1$, $\mathcal{N} = 0.01$, $w = -2/3$, $\gamma = 0.1$, and $\Lambda = 0$, with panel (a) corresponding to $\beta/M = 0.1$ and panel (b) to $\beta/M = 0.2$. The vertical dashed line marks the photon-sphere radius r_{ph} , while the horizontal magenta line denotes the critical value $E_{\text{ph}}^2 = V_{\text{eff}}(r_{\text{ph}})$. The shaded red region indicates the forbidden sector for photons with energy below the potential barrier, whereas the blue region indicates the allowed sector. Changing β/M shifts the height and position of the potential barrier, thereby modifying both the photon-sphere radius and the critical impact parameter.

Figure 6 illustrates the potential-barrier structure that determines the capture and scattering of photons. Panel (a) corresponds to $\beta/M = 0.1$, while panel (b) corresponds to $\beta/M = 0.2$. The peak of V_{eff} identifies the unstable photon orbit and therefore fixes the critical impact parameter b_c . The comparison between the two panels shows that changing the

deformation scale alters both the position and the height of the barrier, which later affects the photon trajectories, the shadow radius, and the high-frequency absorption cross section.

The path of the light ray can be illustrated based on the equation of motion. Combining Eqs. (37) and (38), we obtain

$$\frac{dr}{d\phi} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{r^4}{b^2} - r^2 \left[1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r} + \alpha \left\{ \frac{\beta^2}{3r(\beta+r)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta+r)^2} \right\} - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r^{3w+1}} \right]}, \quad (41)$$

To facilitate integration, we introduce the variable $u(\phi) = 1/r(\phi)$. Thus, Eq. (41) transforms into

$$\frac{du}{d\phi} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{b^2} + \frac{\Lambda}{3} - u^2 \left[1 - \gamma - 2Mu + \alpha \left\{ \frac{\beta^2 u^4}{3(\beta u + 1)^3} + \frac{u^2}{(\beta u + 1)^2} \right\} - \mathcal{N} u^{3w+1} \right]} \equiv \pm \Phi(u, b), \quad (42)$$

where $b = L/E$ is the impact parameter. The geometry of the geodesics is determined by the roots of the equation $\Phi(u) = 0$. Specifically, for $b > b_c$, light is deflected at the radial position u_i satisfying $\Phi(u_i) = 0$. Therefore, determining the radial position u_i is essential for understanding the trajectory of the light ray.

To make the optical interpretation more transparent, Fig. 7 shows representative photon trajectories in the equatorial plane. The curves are obtained by integrating the null geodesic equation for different values of the impact parameter normalized by the critical value $b_c = r_s/\sqrt{f(r_s)}$. The three characteristic regimes are clearly identified. For $b < b_c$, the photon crosses the event horizon and is captured. For $b = b_c$, the trajectory approaches the unstable circular null orbit at the photon sphere. For $b > b_c$, the photon is deflected by the gravitational field and returns to the asymptotic region. This behavior provides the geometric origin of the black-hole shadow, whose boundary is determined by the critical trajectory associated with b_c .

Next, we turn to the study of circular null orbits, with particular emphasis on the photon sphere, and examine how the spacetime's geometric parameters influence its properties. The photon sphere is a spherical hypersurface surrounding a black hole on which photons can move along unstable circular null geodesics. Its radius is highly sensitive to the underlying spacetime geometry and, consequently, to the black hole parameters.

For circular null geodesics, the conditions $\dot{r} = 0$, $\ddot{r} = 0$ must be simultaneously satisfied. Using Eq. (39), these conditions lead to the following relations:

$$E^2 = V_{\text{eff}}(r) = \frac{L^2}{r^2} f(r), \quad (43)$$

which gives the critical impact parameter b_c at $r = r_{\text{ph}}$. In addition,

$$\frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{f(r)}{r^2} \right) = 0. \quad (44)$$

FIG. 7. Photon trajectories in the equatorial plane for different values of the normalized impact parameter b/b_c . The black disk represents the event horizon, while the dashed circle denotes the photon sphere. For $b < b_c$, photons are captured by the black hole; for $b = b_c$, the trajectory approaches the unstable circular null orbit; and for $b > b_c$, photons are scattered back to large distances. The parameters are fixed as $M = 1$, $\alpha = 1$, $\beta/M = 0.1$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $\mathcal{N}M = 0.01$, $w = -2/3$, and $\Lambda M^2 = -0.03$. This plot illustrates the geometric origin of the shadow boundary, which is determined by the critical trajectory.

The relation Eq. (44) gives the photon-sphere radius $r = r_s$, which satisfies the following algebraic equation:

$$1 - \gamma - \frac{3M}{r} + \alpha \left[\frac{\beta^2(\beta + 2r)}{2r(\beta + r)^4} + \frac{\beta + 2r}{(\beta + r)^3} \right] - \frac{(3w + 3)}{2} \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r^{3w+1}} = 0. \quad (45)$$

This is the corrected photon-sphere equation obtained directly from $d(f/r^2)/dr = 0$. The exact analytical solution of the above algebraic equation in r_s is complicated. However, one can determine the numerical results by selecting suitable values of various parameters.

TABLE I. Variation of photon sphere radius r_{ph}/M with parameters β and γ , while keeping $\alpha/M^2 = 1$, $\mathcal{N} = 0.01/M$, $w = -2/3$ fixed.

$\beta/M(\downarrow) \setminus \gamma(\rightarrow)$	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25
0.1	2.39304	2.58918	2.80724	3.05203	3.32975
0.2	2.49126	2.67781	2.88720	3.12411	3.39462
0.3	2.56534	2.74669	2.95105	3.18309	3.44890
0.4	2.62437	2.80260	3.00381	3.23267	3.49527
0.5	2.67301	2.84928	3.04843	3.27515	3.53551

Finally, we focus on the black-hole shadow and on how it is affected by the geometric parameters. The black hole

shadow corresponds to the collection of photon trajectories that are captured by the black hole and therefore do not reach a distant observer. It arises as a purely gravitational effect, governed entirely by the behavior of null geodesics in the strong-field region of the spacetime. It represents the apparent dark region on the observer's sky formed by photons that

TABLE II. Variation of photon sphere radius r_s/M with parameters β and \mathcal{N} , while keeping $\alpha/M^2 = 1$, $w = -2/3$, $\gamma = 0.1$ fixed.

$\beta/M(\downarrow) \setminus \mathcal{N}M(\rightarrow)$	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05
0.1	2.58918	2.64454	2.70411	2.76856	2.83872
0.2	2.67781	2.73259	2.79163	2.85563	2.92543
0.3	2.74669	2.80144	2.86052	2.92461	2.99459
0.4	2.80260	2.85757	2.91691	2.98134	3.05175
0.5	2.84928	2.90459	2.96432	3.02920	3.10014

asymptotically approach unstable circular orbits and eventually fall into the black hole.

The angular size of the radius for a static observer located at position r_O is defined by [58]

$$\sin \vartheta_{\text{sh}} = \frac{h(r_s)}{h(r_O)}, \quad h^2(r) = \frac{r^2}{f(r)}. \quad (46)$$

Substituting the metric components, we find

$$\sin \vartheta_{\text{sh}} = \frac{r_s}{r_O} \sqrt{\frac{1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r_O} + \alpha \left[\frac{\beta^2}{3r_O(\beta+r_O)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta+r_O)^2} \right] - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r_O^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r_O^{3w+1}}}{1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r_s} + \alpha \left[\frac{\beta^2}{3r_s(\beta+r_s)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta+r_s)^2} \right] - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r_s^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r_s^{3w+1}}}}. \quad (47)$$

FIG. 8. Static angular radius ϑ_{sh} of the black-hole shadow as a function of the observer position r_0 . The fixed parameters are $\alpha = 1$, $\gamma = 0.1$, $w = -2/3$, and $\Lambda = -0.03$. Panel (a) keeps $\mathcal{N} = 0.01$ fixed and varies the deformation scale β , while panel (b) keeps $\beta = 0.1$ fixed and varies the QF normalization \mathcal{N} . In both panels, ϑ_{sh} decreases as the observer moves farther away from the black hole. The separation among the curves shows that both the deformation scale and the QF normalization modify the apparent angular size through their effect on r_s and on the redshift factor $f(r_0)/f(r_s)$.

FIG. 9. Photon-sphere radius r_s/M as a function of the deformation parameter β/M and the surrounding-matter parameters. Panel (a) shows the β/M - γ dependence for fixed $\mathcal{N} = 0.01/M$, whereas panel (b) shows the β/M - \mathcal{N}/M dependence for fixed $\gamma = 0.1$. The remaining parameters are $M = 1$, $\alpha = 1$, $w = -2/3$, and $\Lambda = -0.03$. The surfaces show that increasing β/M , γ , or \mathcal{N}/M increases the photon-sphere radius in the displayed domain, in agreement with Tables I and II.

Therefore, the shadow radius is given by

$$R_{\text{sh}} \simeq r_O \vartheta_{\text{sh}} = r_s \sqrt{\frac{1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r_O} + \alpha \left[\frac{\beta^2}{3r_O(\beta+r_O)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta+r_O)^2} \right] - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r_O^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r_O^{3w+1}}}{1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r_s} + \alpha \left[\frac{\beta^2}{3r_s(\beta+r_s)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta+r_s)^2} \right] - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r_s^2 - \frac{\mathcal{N}}{r_s^{3w+1}}}}. \quad (48)$$

We note that the approximation implemented in Eq. (48) is valid only for small values of ϑ_{sh} . From the above analysis, we observe that the shadow radius depends on CS parameter γ , QF parameters (\mathcal{N} , w), and the deformation parameters (α , β).

FIG. 10. Shadow radius R_{sh}/M as a function of the deformation parameter β/M and the surrounding-matter parameters. Panel (a) shows the dependence on β/M and γ for fixed $\mathcal{N} = 0.01/M$, while panel (b) shows the dependence on β/M and \mathcal{N}/M for fixed $\gamma = 0.1$. The remaining parameters are $M = 1$, $\alpha = 1$, $w = -2/3$, $\Lambda = -0.03$, and $r_0/M = 10$. The monotonic growth of the surface reflects the fact that the shadow radius inherits the increase of the photon-sphere radius and is further amplified by the redshift factor entering Eq. (48). This behavior is consistent with the numerical values listed in Tables III and IV.

For the specific state parameter $w = -2/3$, the shadow radius simplifies as

$$R_{\text{sh}} \simeq r_O \vartheta_{\text{sh}} = r_s \sqrt{\frac{1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r_O} + \alpha \left[\frac{\beta^2}{3r_O(\beta+r_O)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta+r_O)^2} \right] - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r_O^2 - \mathcal{N}r_O}{1 - \gamma - \frac{2M}{r_s} + \alpha \left[\frac{\beta^2}{3r_s(\beta+r_s)^3} + \frac{1}{(\beta+r_s)^2} \right] - \frac{\Lambda}{3} r_s^2 - \mathcal{N}r_s}}. \quad (49)$$

Figure 8 shows how the static angular radius of the shadow changes with the observer position. In panel (a), increasing β increases the angular radius for a fixed value of \mathcal{N} , while in panel (b), increasing \mathcal{N} produces a similar enlargement for fixed β . For all curves, ϑ_{sh} decreases as r_0 increases, as expected from the geometric dilution of the apparent size with distance. The curves do not collapse to a single profile because the apparent angle depends not only on the photon-sphere radius but also on the ratio $f(r_0)/f(r_s)$ in Eq. (47).

The dependence of the photon-sphere radius on the model parameters is displayed in Fig. 9. Panel (a) confirms that r_s/M grows with both β/M and γ when \mathcal{N} is fixed. Panel (b) shows the same monotonic trend when \mathcal{N}/M is varied at fixed γ . This agrees with Tables I and II, and indicates that the deformation and surrounding fields push the unstable null orbit outward in the explored parameter range.

Figure 10 gives the corresponding behavior of the shadow radius. Panel (a) shows that the increase of γ produces a pronounced growth of R_{sh}/M , while the dependence on β/M is milder but still monotonic. Panel (b) shows that increasing \mathcal{N}/M also enlarges the shadow. Therefore, the shadow radius is controlled by two combined effects: the outward displacement of the photon sphere and the modification of the optical redshift factor entering Eq. (48).

Figure 11 provides a direct graphical comparison between the theoretical shadow radius and the observational intervals quoted above. Panel (a) shows that increasing γ produces a pronounced increase in R_{sh}/M , pushing the curves from the Sgr A* and overlap regions toward and beyond the M87* interval. The color coding indicates that larger β/M produces a mild upward shift of the curves, but this effect is subdominant compared with the variation in γ . Panel (b) confirms this hierarchy: for fixed γ , the shadow radius increases slowly with β/M , whereas different values of γ separate the curves substantially. This behavior is consistent with the numerical tables, where the string-cloud parameter changes both the photon-sphere location and the redshift factor entering Eq. (48).

Since the Event Horizon Telescope (EHT) has measured the angular shadow diameter of the supermassive black holes M87* and Sgr A*, the theoretical shadow radius obtained in the present model can be used to constrain the parameters of the deformed Schwarzschild-AdS black-hole spacetime with CS and QF. For a static and spherically symmetric black hole, the shadow diameter is given by

$$R_{\text{sh}} = \frac{D \Theta_{\text{sh}}}{2M}, \quad (50)$$

where Θ_{sh} represents the angular size of the black hole

FIG. 11. Shadow radius R_{sh}/M compared with the EHT-inferred intervals for M87* and Sgr A*. The blue band corresponds to $R_{\text{sh}}^{\text{M87}^*}/M = 5.5 \pm 0.75$, while the red band corresponds to $R_{\text{sh}}^{\text{Sgr A}^*}/M = 4.75 \pm 0.70$. In panel (a), R_{sh}/M is shown as a function of the string-cloud parameter γ for different values of β/M , with $\alpha = 1$, $\mathcal{N}M = 0.01$, $w = -2/3$, $\Lambda M^2 = -0.03$, and $r_0/M = 10$. In panel (b), R_{sh}/M is shown as a function of β/M for different values of γ and the same remaining parameters. The comparison shows that γ produces a stronger variation of the shadow radius than β/M in the displayed range, so only restricted regions of the representative parameter space overlap with the EHT windows.

TABLE III. Variation of shadow radius R_{sh}/M with parameters β and γ , while keeping $\alpha/M^2 = 1$, $\mathcal{N} = 0.01/M$, $w = -2/3$, $r_0/M = 10$, $\Lambda = -0.03$.

$\beta/M(\downarrow)\backslash\gamma(\rightarrow)$	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25
0.1	5.55017	5.92851	6.33127	6.75716	7.20288
0.2	5.64979	6.01508	6.40553	6.81979	7.25452
0.3	5.72813	6.08478	6.46662	6.87232	7.29863
0.4	5.79237	6.14282	6.51824	6.91734	7.33693
0.5	5.84648	6.19225	6.56268	6.95652	7.37062

TABLE IV. Variation of shadow radius R_{sh}/M with parameters β and \mathcal{N} , while keeping $\alpha/M^2 = 1$, $\gamma = 0.10$, $w = -2/3$, $r_0/M = 10$, $\Lambda = -0.03$.

$\beta/M(\downarrow)\backslash\mathcal{N}M(\rightarrow)$	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05
0.1	5.92851	5.99709	6.07186	6.15407	6.24538
0.2	6.01508	6.08351	6.15825	6.24061	6.33227
0.3	6.08478	6.15342	6.22850	6.31133	6.40365
0.4	6.14282	6.21184	6.28740	6.37084	6.46393
0.5	6.19225	6.26172	6.33783	6.42194	6.51585

shadow, M is the mass of the source, and D is the distance to the source.

For M87*, the EHT Collaboration reported an angular size of the shadow $\Theta_{\text{sh}}^{\text{obs}} = (42 \pm 3) \mu\text{as}$, $D = (16.8 \pm 0.8)\text{Mpc}$, and $M_{\text{M87}^*} = (6.5 \pm 0.7) \times 10^9 M_{\odot}$ [25]. With this data in hand, the shadow diameter of M87* in mass units is given by

$$R_{\text{sh}}^{\text{M87}^*} = (5.5 \pm 0.75)M_{\text{M87}^*}, \quad (51)$$

where the uncertainty was obtained by standard error propa-

gation.

For Sgr A*, from the Keck and Very Large Telescope Interferometer (VLTI) instruments within a 1σ uncertainty, one has $\Theta_s = (48.7 \pm 7) \mu\text{as}$, $M_{\text{Sgr A}^*} = 4 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$, and $D = 8 \text{ kpc}$ [29, 30, 59]. Therefore, the shadow diameter of Sgr A* is given by

$$R_{\text{sh}}^{\text{Sgr A}^*} = (4.75 \pm 0.7)M_{\text{Sgr A}^*}. \quad (52)$$

As the metric function $f(r)$ depends on four free parameters ($\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \mathcal{N}$) for the state parameter $w = -2/3$, a systematic exploration of the parameter space is necessary to constrain physically viable configurations. Deriving the full range of constraints from the observed shadow diameters of M87* and Sgr A* requires a multidimensional scan including parameter degeneracies and propagated uncertainties. Therefore, in the present analysis we fix two of the four parameters and present representative numerical results for the shadow radius in Tables III–IV. From Table III, we observe that for $\gamma = 0.05$ and $\beta/M = 0.1$ – 0.5 , the numerical results fall within the quoted interval for M87*. However, this should be interpreted as an indicative consistency check rather than a complete observational bound. A stronger constraint would require a global likelihood analysis over $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \mathcal{N}, w)$, together with a careful discussion of the applicability of an AdS background to astrophysical black holes.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

We have investigated a deformed Schwarzschild–AdS black hole surrounded by a cloud of strings and immersed in a quintessence field. The matter content and notation were kept consistent with the lapse function: γ denotes the string-cloud parameter, (\mathcal{N}, w) describe the quintessence sector, and (α, β) control the geometric deformation. This unified nota-

tion avoids mixing the quintessence interpretation with unrelated perfect-fluid dark-matter terminology.

From the thermodynamic side, we derived the entropy, Hawking temperature, mass parameter, thermodynamic volume, generalized first law, conjugate potentials, and Smarr relation in the extended phase space. The dimensionless nature of γ explains its absence from the Euler-type Smarr formula. We also analyzed the behavior of the Hawking temperature and showed that the AdS term generates a minimum-temperature structure, while γ and \mathcal{N} lower the temperature branch for the representative choice $w = -2/3$. We also emphasized that the limit $\beta \rightarrow 0$ with $\alpha = Q^2$ recovers a charged-like AdS geometry, in which the deformation parameter behaves as an effective charge squared. Away from this limit, however, the deformation is not simply equivalent to an electromagnetic charge.

We also formulated the sparsity of Hawking radiation for the present geometry. In the geometric-optics approximation, the high-frequency absorption cross section is determined by the critical impact parameter of the photon sphere, $\sigma_{\text{lim}} = \pi r_s^2 / f(r_s)$. Combining this cross section with the Hawking temperature yields the sparsity parameter η in Eq. (28). The numerical behavior displayed in Fig. 4 shows that $\eta > 1$ throughout the explored region, confirming that the Hawking flux remains sparse rather than continuous. This result shows that the radiation rate is controlled not only by the temperature but also by the optical structure of the space-time.

For the optical sector, we derived the null geodesic equations, corrected the impact-parameter notation, and obtained the photon-sphere condition from $d(f/r^2)/dr = 0$. The numerical tables and plots show that, for the representative parameter choices considered here, increasing β , γ , or \mathcal{N} increases both the photon-sphere radius and the shadow radius. The shadow analysis was then compared with the EHT-inferred intervals for M87* and Sgr A*. Some parameter choices, especially those with small γ , are compatible with the M87* interval, but the result should be regarded as a consistency check rather than a complete observational constraint.

Future work should extend the present analysis in three directions. First, a full parameter-space scan should be performed to obtain robust bounds on $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \mathcal{N}, w)$. Second, the thermodynamic stability and critical behavior should be analyzed beyond representative limits, especially near the charged-like $\beta \rightarrow 0$ sector. Third, the observational comparison should incorporate realistic astrophysical effects, including rotation, plasma, accretion-flow modeling, and the fact that asymptotically AdS behavior is an idealized approximation for the environments of M87* and Sgr A*.

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